

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Begmatova Sarvinoz Shavkat qizi

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF SIMPLE SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK (IN THE EXAMPLE
OF SOCIAL NETWORKS)

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

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2023-2024

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